

Kinetics, mechanism and thermodynamic studies of rhodium(III) catalysed oxidation of alanine by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III)

P. K. Chourasia*, N. C. Bhattacharjee and T. K. Singh

Department of Chemistry, Magadh University, Bodh Gaya-824 234, Bihar, India

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Abstract : The kinetics and mechanism of rhodium(III) catalysed oxidation of alanine in alkaline solution of hexacyanoferrate(III) have been studied. The kinetic data shows zero order dependence on each hexacyanoferrate(III) and sodium hydroxide whereas first order dependence each on alanine and Rh^{III}. Negligible effect of ionic strength of the medium has been reported. A suitable mechanism consistent with the observed kinetics has been suggested.

Keywords : Rhodium(III), mechanism, hexacyanoferrate(III), alanine.

Introduction

Some works on Ru^{III} 1-5 and Os^{VIII} 6,7 catalysed oxidation by hexacyanoferrate(III) have been reported. Since little work has been reported on Rh^{III} catalysis⁸ in ferricyanide and *N*-bromo-acetamide oxidation⁹, the authors undertook the detailed study of Rh^{III} catalysed oxidation of alanine by hexacyanoferrate(III) in an alkaline medium.

Results and discussion

The observed rate constant (k_0), was found to be independent of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$ and $[\text{OH}^-]$, indicating that the reaction is zero order with respect to both hexacyanoferrate(III) and OH^- [Tables 1(a) and 1(b)]¹¹. The rate was found to increase with an increase in the concentra-

tion of alanine. The observed rate constant k_0 was found to be proportional to $[\text{Alanine}]$ (Table 2a) and a plot of k_0 vs $[\text{Alanine}]$ at 308 K was found to be a straight line passing through the origin, indicating a first order dependence of the rate on $[\text{Alanine}]$. The rate also found to be proportional to $[\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}]_0$, indicating a first order dependence on $[\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}]_0$ (Table 2b).

The effect of ionic strength on the zero order rate constant (k_0) is negligible as evident from Table 3. The effect of temperature on the reaction rate was studied at four different temperatures with variation of $[\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]$, but keeping $[\text{Alanine}]$, $[\text{NaOH}]$ and $[\text{RhCl}_3]$ unchanged (Table 4).

Table 1(a). Variation of observed rate constant with oxidant concentration

[Alanine] = 1.00×10^{-2} mol dm ⁻³ , [NaOH] 1.50×10^{-2} mol dm ⁻³ , $[\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}]_0 = 3.20 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm ⁻³ , Temp. = 308 K						
$[\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6] \times 10^3$ (mol dm ⁻³)	1.00	1.25	1.66	2.00	2.50	4.00
$10^7 k_0$ (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	3.00	3.08	2.96	3.02	3.10	3.08

Table 1(b). Variation of observed rate constant with concentration of NaOH

$[\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6] = 2.00 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹ , [Alanine] = 1.00×10^{-2} mol dm ⁻³ , $[\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}]_0 = 3.2 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm ⁻³ , Temp. = 308 K						
$[\text{NaOH}] \times 10^2$ (mol dm ⁻³)	0.75	1.00	1.50	2.00	3.00	4.00
$10^7 k_0$ (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	3.04	3.02	3.02	3.08	3.10	3.02

Table 2(a). Dependence of observed rate constant on the concentration of alanine

$[\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6] = 1.25 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm ⁻³ , [NaOH] = 1.50×10^{-2} mol dm ⁻³ , $[\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}]_0 = 3.2 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm ⁻³ , Temp. = 308 K						
$[\text{Alanine}] \times 10^2$ (mol dm ⁻³)	0.75	1.00	1.50	2.00	3.00	3.75
$10^7 k_0$ (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	2.20	3.08	4.52	6.18	9.26	11.50
$10^5 k_0/[\text{Alanine}]$ (s ⁻¹)	2.93	3.08	3.03	3.09	3.08	3.06

$$v = \frac{k_1 k_2}{(k_{-1} + k_2) + k_1 [s]} [s][\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}]_0 \quad (7)$$

since $[s] \sim 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, if k_1 be small such that $k_1 [s] \ll k_{-1} + k_2$, then eq. (7) rearranges to

$$v = -\frac{k_1 k_2}{(k_{-1} + k_2)} [s][\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}]_0 = k_0 \quad (8)$$

where k_0 is the observed rate constant.

Also

$$\frac{k_0}{[S][\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}]_0} = \frac{k_1 k_2}{(k_{-1} + k_2)} = k_3 \text{ (constant)} \quad (9)$$

It is evident from eq. (8) that a plot of k_0 vs $[s]$ should be a straight line passing through the origin as has been found experimentally. Eq. (8) also demands a plot of k_0 vs $[\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}]_0$ to be linear passing through the origin which is also an experimental fact (Table 2b). Since the reaction involves two neutral species, it is expected that the ionic strength should have negligible effect on the reaction rate and this also has been verified experimentally. Thus all the kinetic observations support the mechanism of the reaction.

Experimental

The sample of alanine (S. Merck) and NaOH (S. Merck) were employed and their solution were prepared in double distilled water. A.R. (B.D.H.) and hexacyanoferrate(III) of GR (S. Merck) were used. The sample of rhodium(III) chloride (Johnson Matthey) was prepared by dissolving the sample in a known strength of HCl (A.R.) and finally making it up adding a required amount of double distilled water. The final strength of HCl and rhodium chloride was kept 1 N and $1.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ respectively.

The solutions of required amount of hexacyanoferrate(III), sodium hydroxide and catalytic rhodium(III)

chloride were mixed together and kept at 308 K. The solution of alanine was also kept at 308 K. The reaction mixture was prepared by mixing both the solutions. The standard method of estimation of hexacyanoferrate(III) was applied for the reaction mixture. Stoichiometric experiments showed that 2 moles of hexacyanoferrate(III) were consumed by one mole of alanine. All kinetic measurements were performed as described earlier⁹.

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